

Flaws in the vitamin C and common cold meta-analysis by Ran et al. (2020)

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Ran et al. have not responded to the PubPeer comment by 2026.

Comment on:

Li Ran, Wenli Zhao, Hongwu Wang, Ye Zhao, Huaïen Bu.

Vitamin C as a Supplementary Therapy in Relieving Symptoms of the Common Cold: A Meta-Analysis of 10 Randomized Controlled Trials.

Biomed Res Int. 2020; 2020: 8573742.

<https://doi.org/10.1155/2020/8573742>

<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/pmc7569434>

There are numerous problems in the meta-analysis by Ran et al. [1].

The authors write in the inclusion criteria (2.2) that they included trials with “*vitamin C as a therapeutic technique with antiviral therapies*”.

However, there is no description of what Ran et al. mean by “antiviral therapies” [1]. There are no known antivirals for the common cold. Furthermore, over decades, vitamin C has been indicated in drug metabolism [2,3], and therefore it is even possible that the undefined “antivirals” may cause adverse effects, such that any possible effects of vitamin C might be targeting harms due to the “antivirals”, and not the symptoms of the respiratory virus infection.

Transparency is a fundamental principle in science. Ran et al. pool 10 Chinese trials, but it is not possible to check the methods of any of those 10 trials (references 21 to 30 in [1]). A Google search does not identify any of them.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17085738> Reports on scurvy uploaded to Zenodo by Harri Hemilä

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19791426> Misleading and erroneous papers on vitamin C; a list by Harri Hemilä

It is possible to arrange translation of non-English papers to English, so that readers can check what the original publication actually stated in the methods and results. Ideally, Ran et al. could have included the translations in a supplement. In this respect there is a serious problem with transparency. Ran et al. write: “*Data Availability: Data are all contained within the paper*” [1]. This is not correct. It is not possible to trace where the data in the forest plots come from.

The diagnosis of the common cold is based on symptoms such as runny nose, cough and/or sore throat, etc. Therefore, placebo-control and blinding at all stages of the trial from allocation to outcome assessment is essential in controlled trials on the common cold. However, for every one of the 10 included trials, “allocation concealment”, “blinding of participants and personnel” and “blinding of outcome assessment” are assessed as “unclear” (Table 2 in [1]). Thus, it is possible that observations were seriously biased by patients and/or researchers knowing who was getting which treatment.

In the results section, Ran et al. state that “*All studies were 100% completed and had no bias in selective reporting.*” This is based on Table 2, which states “low risk” for all 10 included trials for “incomplete outcome data” and “selective reporting”. However, Figures 3 and 4 show only 5 of the 10 included trials. Is there incomplete outcome data and/or selective reporting in the 5 trials that are not included in Figures 3 and 4, or why are those trials not shown?

The title states “10 randomized controlled trials” [1]. However, Table 2 shows that “random sequence generation” was “unclear” in 7 out of the 10 included trials. In the Results section, Ran et al. state that “*Only three articles demonstrated that a random sequence was generated with random number tables, and there was no detailed information in the remaining seven.*”

All 10 included studies were Chinese trials. There have been serious concerns about the validity of reporting of Chinese controlled trials: “*Most reports of randomized controlled trials published in some Chinese journals lacked an adequate description of randomization. Similarly, most so called 'randomized controlled trials' were not real randomized controlled trials owing to a lack of adequate understanding on the part of the authors of rigorous clinical trial design*” [4]. Thus, the title appears misleading as there is no guarantee that 7 of the 10 included trials actually were randomized trials. In addition, there is strong evidence of publication bias of Chinese trials [5].

Thus, Ran et al. should have questioned the validity of the 7 trials with no details about the method of allocation, and of all 10 trials because there was no evidence of any level of blinding.

Figure 3 shows the effect of vitamin C on “symptom alleviation” and Figure 4 shows the effect on “time for healing”. However, Ran et al. do not describe the difference between these two outcomes. It would seem evident that when symptoms are alleviated, the patient is healed [1].

In the Abstract, Ran et al. summarize the findings as follows: “*The total efficacy (RR = 1.27, 95% CI (1.08, 1.48), P = 0.003), the time for symptom amelioration (MD= -15.84, 95% CI (-17.02, -14.66), P < 0.00001), and the time for healing (I, 95% CI (-14.98, -4.22), P = 0.0005) were better with vitamin C*”.

However, nowhere in the paper is there a description of what “total efficacy” measures. The RR is calculated from “events” in Figure 2, but there is no description of what the “event” is. The common cold is self-limited [1, p.1] and all patients are cured over time. Therefore, the proportion who are cured is 100% in all common cold patients and this leads to RR (risk ratio) = 1.00 for the comparison of being cured in two groups. Thus, it is not clear what RR = 1.27 means.

Furthermore, measurements should show the unit of measurement. However, the Abstract and the main text do not describe whether “MD= -15.84” means hours or days or percentages or something else. In the abstract, the effect on the time of healing is reported as “I” (see paragraph above) which indicates poor reading of the manuscript and proofs by the 5 authors.

Usually common cold lasts on average some 7 days [6] and Ran et al. also write in their Introduction that “*common cold is self-limited and lasts between seven and ten days*” [1, p.1]. However, the distribution of common cold duration is wide, with some colds lasting just 1 day, and some lasting over 3 weeks. In our Cochrane review we calculated from a few dozen trials reporting the SD, that the ratio of SD to mean was on average some 0.7 [7, p.8]. However, in the control groups of Figure 4 [1], the ratio of SD to mean is 0.12 or less for all the 5 trials, which is not believable given the wide distribution in the common cold duration.

Reference 22 is puzzling: H. Gao and M. H. Wang, “*The analysis of the clinical efficacy of inhalation of vitamin C injection in the treatment of pediatric upper respiratory tract infection,*” World Latest Medicine Information, vol. 14, no. 1, p. 192, 2014.”

What does inhalation of vitamin C injection mean? The text section [1] does not mention that the method of administration of vitamin C was highly unusual in the Gao and Wang trial.

Finally, Ran et al. failed to refer to earlier and more extensive meta-analyses on vitamin C and the common cold [7,8]. Even more strange is the failure to refer to their own earlier meta-analysis on vitamin C and the common cold [9].

In conclusion, there are several issues that challenge the validity of the review by Ran et al. [1].

References

1. Li Ran, Wenli Zhao, Hongwu Wang, Ye Zhao, Huaien Bu. Vitamin C as a Supplementary Therapy in Relieving Symptoms of the Common Cold: A Meta-Analysis of 10 Randomized Controlled Trials. Biomed Res Int. 2020; 2020: 8573742.
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This paper:

Ran, Li, Zhao, Wenli, Wang, Jingxia, Wang, Hongwu, Zhao, Ye, Tseng, Yiider, Bu, Huaien, [Retracted] Extra Dose of Vitamin C Based on a Daily Supplementation Shortens the Common Cold: A Meta-Analysis of 9 Randomized Controlled Trials, BioMed Research International, 2018, 1837634, 12 pages, 2018.

was later retracted in 2023:

<https://doi.org/10.1155/2023/9848057>

“BioMed Research International and the authors have retracted the article titled “Extra Dose of Vitamin C Based on a Daily Supplementation Shortens the Common Cold: A Meta-Analysis of 9 Randomized Controlled Trials” [1] due to a fundamental error identified in the calculations underlying the conclusions, as raised by readers of the article, Dr. Colby Vorland and Dr. Andrew Brown of the Indiana University School of Public Health-Bloomington, and **Dr. Harri Hemilä of the University of Helsinki, summarized on PubPeer:**”

<https://pubpeer.com/publications/077EAB95E9141BE6A455C30F0A688E>